

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B245
 Date: 21st Sep 2006
 Take Off: 10:09:40
 Landing: 15:06:43
 Flight Time: 5h57m03s

Campaign: Visurb

Operating Area: Coastal; East Anglia to SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCM2 / Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Wet Neph	Martin Glew	Met Office
9	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
10	SID2	Richard Greenaway	University of Hertford
11	Obs	Mike Collins	Directflight
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B245

Date: 21 September 2006

Project: VISURB

Location: Sout & East coasts

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093310		INU	0.59 kft	127	to nav 52'04.36N 0'37.48W
093921		GPS	0.59 kft	127	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
094050		CGPS	0.60 kft	127	logging B245cgps.log
095723	100101	Orbit 1	0.61 kft	176	BBR runway orbit station 180M
095951		Video	0.61 kft	297	#1 Rfc #2 Ufc
100135		ASP	0.61 kft	175	open
100940		T/O	0.59 kft	210	Cranfield
101015		psap	1.3 kft	228	flow on
101031		Heimann	1.4 kft	280	shutter open
101643		transit	10.0 kft	064	FL 100
102500	103632	Profile 1	10.0 - 0.24 kft	001	50 ft
102556		BBR	9.1 kft	000	extend
102706		dry neph	8.0 kft	012	DLU set to 'no packets', reset satisfied
103031		P1	4.8 kft	098	interrupt
103122		P1	4.8 kft	109	resumed
103633	104058	Profile 2	0.24 - 3.3 kft	128	50 ft qnh 1009
104107	104335	Run 1	3.3 kft	125	
104123		bbr	3.3 kft	149	retract
104147		Nev	3.3 kft	181	zero
104335	104607	Profile 2	3.3 - 1.1 kft	181	
104608	110040	Run 2.1	1.1 kft	181	towards waypoint 41
104659		!	1.1 kft	180	1000ft qnh1011
104719		nev	1.1 kft	180	zero
104806		JW	1.1 kft	181	zero
105004		heimann	1.1 kft	181	cal 10
110040	110517	Run 2.2	1.1 kft	190	waypoint 41
110517	110657	Profile 3	1.1 - 0.65 kft	192	
110657	111504	Run 3.1	0.65 - 0.73 kft	191	towards waypoint 42
111505	112810	Run 3.2	0.73 - 0.70 kft	196	waypoint 42 waypoint 43 qnh 1005
112810	114251	Run 3.3	0.70 - 0.80 kft	249	waypoint 43 qnh 1005 waypoint 44 qnh 1003
114252	120004	Run 3.4	0.80 - 0.81 kft	250	waypoint 44 qnh 1003 waypoint 45 qnh 1002
120004	120620	Profile 4	0.81 - 6.5 kft	263	waypoint 45 qnh 1002
120621	121300	Run 4.1	6.5 kft	258	
121350		!	6.5 kft	067	end of run @121230
121653	122339	Profile 5	6.5 - 0.86 kft	108	
122339	123003	Run 5.1	0.86 - 0.89 kft	096	waypoint 45
122409		Heimann	0.88 kft	097	cal 10
123003	124350	Run 5.2	0.89 - 0.84 kft	054	waypoint 45 waypoint 44 qnh 1002
124350	130130	Run 5.3	0.84 - 0.75 kft	069	waypoint 44 qnh 1002 waypoint 43 1005
130130	131410	Run 5.4	0.75 kft	070	waypoint 43 1005 waypoint 42 qnh 1006
130751		video	0.73 kft	060	#5 Rfc #6 Ufc started
131410	132643	Run 5.5	0.75 - 0.78 kft	056	waypoint 42 qnh 1006 waypoint 41 qnh 1007
132644	133341	Profile 6	0.78 - 7.5 kft	013	waypoint 41 qnh 1007
133551	134353	Profile 7	7.5 - 0.69 kft	177	
134408	134433	Run 6.1	0.73 kft	174	
134801	135953	Run 6.2	0.71 - 0.63 kft	352	waypoint 41 waypoint 40
135954	140736	Run 6.3	0.63 - 0.72 kft	325	waypoint 40 waypoint 87

140736	141702	Run 6.4	0.72 - 0.77 kft	314 waypoint 87 waypoint 80
141811	144001	Run 6.5	0.72 - 0.74 kft	131
144001	144957	Profile 8	0.74 - 10.0 kft	205
144040		P8	1.2 kft	213 interrupt
144155		P8	1.2 kft	254 resume
144234		Video	2.0 kft	249 #5, #6 end
145025		!	10.0 kft	244 end of science
145406		ASP	10.0 kft	243 closed
150229		heimann	2.9 kft	204 closed
150242		bbr	2.9 kft	207 extend
150643		Land	0.68 kft	208
150851	151153	Orbit 2	0.69 - 0.70 kft	359 runway bbr orbit star t 360M
151628		gps	0.70 kft	306 52'04.36N 0'37.48W
152014		inu	0.70 kft	306 52'03.81N 0'35.66W

B245 Track 21-SEP-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

VISURB-UK: Assessment of aerosol properties related to urban visibility

Flight No: B245

Date: 21st Sept 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on visibility.

Location:

Over ocean areas downwind of major pollution sources. Areas to from off the coast of the Fens (point 87) to the south coast (point 46).

Points:

#87: 53N, 1E.

#40: 5250N, 1.5E.

#41: 5153N, 1.47E.

#42: 5105N, 1.3E.

#43: 5040N, 1.0W.

#44: 5040N, 1.00W.

#45: 5001N, 2.0W.

#46: 5001N, 3.25W.

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Clear skies preferred, but not essential.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer

AMS

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:00Z (11:00L).
2. Transit and then perform a profile descent at 1000ft/min to 50ft at point #87 [30mins].
3. Perform SLR at altitude to be determined by the mission scientist (likely 1000ft -> 4000ft from:
4. #87 -> #40 [10mins, T=40mins].
5. #40 -> #41 [20mins, T=60mins].
6. #41 -> #42 [20mins, T=80mins].
7. #42 -> #43 [10mins, T=90mins].
8. #43 -> #44 [20mins, T=110mins].
9. #44 -> #45 [20mins, T=130mins].
10. #45 -> #46 [15mins, T=145mins].
11. Reciprocal turn [5mins, T=150mins].

12. Perform a SLR from #46 -> #87 via the points specified in point 5-9 [90mins, T=240mins].
13. Progress further up the coast in a northerly direction as time allows [10mins, 250mins].
14. Recover to Cranfield [20mins, 270mins]

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B245

Date: 21/09/2006

Sortie Objectives: VISURB flying. To assess the performance of the aerosol and visibility forecasts in the Met Office Mesoscale model. In addition to make ground manoeuvres to examine the response of the BBRs as a function of relative sun-aircraft azimuth angle.

Operating area: Ocean areas close to the coast of the UK from Humberside to Devon.

Weather: A moderate/strong southerly wind was affecting the operating area advecting aerosol from the continent towards the UK. To the west there was significant cloud associated with a frontal system, while to the east was free from cloud. Generally, cloud only affected the radiation measurements to the west of the Isle of Wight.

Flight Patterns: A pirouette was performed on the old runway pre-flight to determine the effect of aerosol upon the BBRs. Subsequent to take off a transit was performed towards AMPEP point #87, followed by a profile descent to 50ft. The profile showed fairly clean atmospheric conditions, but with some aerosol present to about 7000ft. The main aerosol layer was contained at altitudes of lower than 2000ft, which was certainly affected by pollution as the aerosol and the CO was well-correlated. A SLR was then started in a clockwise direction around the UK. After starting a SLR at 3000ft the level was quickly adjusted to 1000ft, and then to 500ft to put the aircraft in a reasonably polluted layer. The aircraft then transited all the way to point #45 before making a profile ascent to point #46. All of this run was performed at 500ft. For the majority of this run, the BBR data could be used as there was very little interference from cloud except to the west of the Isle of Wight. The aerosol concentrations were not particularly high throughout the majority of this run with green nephelometer scattering levels of only $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ along much of this run. A profile ascent was then performed to FL65 followed by a reciprocal turn and a profile descent back to 500ft. A SLR at 50ft was then performed in an anticlockwise direction around the UK retracing the steps of the clockwise run. Aerosol levels picked up significantly between point #43 and point #42 indicating that aerosol had been advected in from the continent since the SLR in the previous direction. A profile ascent from point #41 to FL70 followed by a reciprocal turn and a profile descent down to point #41. The aerosol scattering was about $30 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ at 500ft and the pollution was contained within the lowest 2000ft of the atmosphere. There was a distinct clear slot at 2000ft and then low levels of pollution in the region 3000-7000ft. The 500ft run anticlockwise around the UK was then restarted. The aerosol scattering peaked close to point #40 at $40\text{-}50 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$. The aerosol concentrations then fell by a factor of 5 or so as point #78 was reached and remained low on the northward progression around the coast. The plume was then intercepted once again as the aircraft turned back southwards towards the UK. The aircraft then performed a profile ascent before recovering to Cranfield. Subsequent to landing a post-flight pirouette was performed which confirmed that the BBRs did indeed have a different pattern in terms of the response as a function of the relative azimuth angle between the sun and the aircraft heading.

Summary: A successful flight – BBR data should be useable. The main plume was intercepted close to the Essex/Suffolk/Norfolk coast which was similar to that predicted by the Mesoscale model. The pirouette manoeuvres proved successful in diagnosing that the BBRs get dirty during flying in pollution which compromises their performance.

Problems: None noted.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

HAYWOOD

Flight No **B.245**.....

Date **21st Sept 2006**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					No cloud at all
					Clear blue skies
					Will do pirouette pre-flight to test
					BBRs - newly cleaned.
	St Pirouette		180°		Start pirouette. Time ~ 9:58Z.
					Clear from all obstacles.
					No cloud above
					Very good circle - should be
					perfect for BBR checking.
	End		179°		<div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
				Time =	
				09:56 → 10:01:20	
					Solar azim = 144° during INS heading
					As is.
					Haze layer at 8000ft, no neph
					to check.
	PI	FL100 ↓	41		
	Int PI	FL50			Interrupt for setting cabin.
	Rest PI	FL50 ↓			Restart.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...245**.....

 Date **21st Sept 2006**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	End P1 St P2				End P1 / St P2
					Sea state ~ 5.
	End P2 St R1	3000ft			Run in a clear slot.
10:43:35	End R1 St P3				
10:46:08	End P3 St R2	1000ft			Somewhat higher concentrations but nothing much. Neph scat $\sim 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, along this run.
	End R2.2 St P3	1000ft ↓			
11:06:57	End P3 St R2.1	500ft			Neph increasing. Sea-state ~ 3. Wind 8 ms^{-1} 168 degrees.
11:15:04	End R3.1 St R3.2				Restart At point #42.
11:17					Turbulence here. $T \sim 28^\circ \text{C}$ $T_a \sim 15^\circ \text{C}$.
					Still completely cloud-free
11:28:40	End R3.2 St R3.3				Way-point #43. Sea state 5, wind 14 ms^{-1} , 130° Cloud just visible to the west - no interference with BBRs.
11:42:52	End R3.3 St R3.4	500ft			At #44. Cloud starting to Sea state #6 interfere with upper BBR.
12:00:04	End S.4 St P4	500ft ↑			#45.
	End P4 St R4				
12:13:15	End R4	6500ft			Turn onto reciprocal.

Cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...245**

 Date **21st Sept 2006**

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 Cloud
 ↑
 ↓
 Cloud Free

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:16:53	St P5	6500 ↓		50N, 3W	Start profile down to 500ft.
12:23:33	End P5 St RS.1	500ft		50N, 2°24W	
12:27					Brief turbulence
12:28	St S.2 End S.3				#45, ship spike in neph.
12:41					Windspeed 21ms^{-1} sea state 6.
12:43:50	End S.2 St S.3	500ft →			#44
13:01:	End S.3 St S.4	500ft →			#43
13:12					Near Dover - lots of ships.
13:14:10	End RS.4 St RS.5	500ft →			#42
13:26:44	End RS.5 St P6	500ft ↑			#41
13:33:41	End P6	FL75 →			Reciprocal turn-back down to point #41
13:35:51	St P7	FL75 ↓			
13:43:	End P7	500ft			

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.245**.....

 Date ..21st Sept 2006...

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:59:40					#40 Abeam. Nephelometer green = $40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
					#87, nephelometer peak of $\sim 50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, falls off to $10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at Blakeney point.
					Out of thick aerosol layer.
	End R64				Turn back towards point #40.
14:18:11	St R6.5			53 ^{30'} N, 0, 30'E	Sea-states 5/6. 15 ms^{-1} / 147° Neph rises from $10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ to $30 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
14:30					T=18°, Td=16 → much higher RH.
14:35					Neph $50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at this time.
14:40:01	End R6.5 / St P8				At #40. Start profile.
14:40:30	Int P8				Int P1 (traffic) Top of pollution layer at 2500ft
14:49:	End P8				End Profile

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B245**

 COOLER
OUT
PRE Date **21/09/06**
~~HEATER~~

 Operator's name: **M. GLEW**

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								ARRIVE (-LIGHT - PARKED) TO BOTH NEPHS, WET on 7, Dry on 1
								SHUT DOWN TO LABVIEW LABVIEW TO RECORD TO B245 directory, when came back
								COULD NOT TALK TO DRY NEPH. SHUT DOWN FOR TAKE OFF.
10435	R2	3000'	11.2	Water in chiller but not on. Only NEPH on HORACE				
								BUT NOT PC. WET NEPH ON PC. SOOPY ON SPARE PC.
10460	R2	1000'	11.1	Chiller off				
10495	R2			Chiller on, WATER at 22°				set Ramping to 5°
10525	R2	1000'	11.0	36%	53.3	↑	+25°C	
10545	R2	1000'	11.0	35.2%	59.1%	↑	+30°C	
10540	R2	1000'	10.9	35.1%	66.2%	↑	+35°C	Humidity set to 102%
10585	R2	1000'	11.0	35.5%	74.4%	↑	+40°C	
11005	R2	1000'	10.3	35.9%	85%	↑	+45°C	Labview errors (Scan from string error) - continue
11040				Chiller off for descent, R/A				and it ran ok
				Measured at 41% in wet neph				
				P3 1000' ↓ Chiller off 42%				
11065	R3.1	500'	10.2	35.0	92%	↓	+38°C	Chiller set to 0°C
11130	R3.1	500'	10.4	34.8%	79.2%	↓	+39°C	chiller set to 0°C
11150	R3.2	500'	10.5	35.3%	69%	↓	+16°C	
11180	R3.2	500'	10.4	40%	64.3%	↓	+11.8°C	
11195	R3.2	500'	10.5	45.8%	62%	↑	+19°C	Chiller set to +20°C

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.245**

 Date **21/09/06**
 (COOLANT OUT)

 Operator's name: **M. GLEW**

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
112200	R3.2	500'	10.4	45.4%	67.4%	↑	+25°C	
112347	R3.2	500'	10.3	46.3%	71.3%	↑	+30°C	
112540	R3.2	500'	10.3	44.2%	77.1%	↑	+35°C	
112715	R3.2	500'	10.2	43.4%	82.7%	↑	+40°C	
112810	R3.3	500'	10.2	32.9%	87.4%	↑	+40°C	
112918	R3.3	500'	10.3	33.7%	89.1%	↑	+45°C	
113215	R3.3	500'	10.4	33.3%	94.1%	↓	+45°C	Chiller to +1.8°C
113500	R3.3	500'	10.4	33.1	90.8%	↓	+29°C	
113800	R3.3	500'	10.3	32.9%	81.9%	↓	+20°C	
1140	240	WET NEPH						
114200	R3.3	500'	10.3	33.7	68.4%	↓	+13°C	Ch
114252	R3.4	500'	10.3	33.5	67.8%	↑	+25°C	
114530	R3.4	500'	10.4	32.7	75.5%	↑	+30°C	
114731	R3.4	500'	10.4	33.1	80.2%	↑	+35°C	
114920	R3.4	500'	10.3	32.7%	86.0%	↑	+40°C	
115100	R3.4	500'	10.2	33.8%	92.6%	↑	+45°C	
115300	R3.4	500'	10.2	33.4%	93.9%	↓	+35°C	chiller to +0°C
115700	R3.4	500'	10.2	33.8%	86.8%	↓	+24°C	
120004	P4	500' ↑	10.1	34.4%	72.8%			Chiller off for profile
121653	P5	↓	10.4	33.6%	51.5%			Chiller off

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B245**.....

 Date **21/09/06**.....
 COOLER OUT

 Operator's name: **M. O'LEW**.....

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
RJ-1	12238		10.3	32.4	58.3	↓	+22°C	Chiller on, set to 0°C
	122630	RJ-1	10.4	32.5	62.2	↑	+25°C	Chiller to +25°C
	122847	RJ-1	10.3	32.2	65.7	↑	+30°C	
	123030	RJ-1	10.5	32.2	71.1	↑	+35°C	
	123920	RJ-1	10.3	33.3	88.3	↓	+40°C	
	124200	RJ-1	10.3	33.2	90.5	↑	+45°C	
	124800	RJ.3	10.4	33.4	95.1	↓	+45°C	Chiller to +0°C
	125110	RJ.3	10.4	33.6	76.5	↓	+20°C	
	125600	RJ.3	10.5	33.7	63.5	↑	+20°C	Chiller to +25°C
	125834	RJ.3	10.4	33.7	69.7	↑	+30°C	
	130100	RJ.3	10.4	33.7	79.0	↑	+35°C	
	130300	RJ.3	10.5	33.7	81.7	↑	+40°C	
	130500	RJ.3	10.4	33.5	88.9	↑	+45°C	
	130730	RJ.3	10.5	33.8	94.1	↓	+39°C	Chiller to 0°C
	131200	RJ.3	10.5	33.5	84.5	↓	+24°C	
	131730	RJ.?	10.4	33.6	63.0	↑	+14°C	Chiller to +25°C
	131920	RJ	10.5	33.1	69.7	↑	+30°C	
	132130	RJ	10.4	32.4	76.3	↑	+35°C	
	132320		10.4	32.7	82.9	↑	+40°C	
	132500		10.4	32.4	88.4	↑	+45°C	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B245**.....

 Date **21/09/06**
 COOLER OUT

 Operator's name: **M. ABR**.....

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph -RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
132644	R6	↑	10.2	32.4	93.2			Chiller off for profile
134520	R6	500'	10.1	30.8	89.0%	↓	+25	Chiller to +3.9°C
134930	R6	500'	10.1	30.1	69.5%	↑	+18°C	Chiller to +25°C
135100	R6	500'	10.2	29.7	73.2%	↑	+30°C	
135310	R6	500'	10.2	30.2	77.9%	↑	+35°C	
135500	R6	500'	10.1	29.7	84.3%	↑	+40°C	
135650	R6	500'	10.1	29.7	90.3%	↑	+45°C	
135910	R6	500'	10.1	30.1	94.1%	↓	+42°C	Chiller to +0°C
140310	R6	500'	10.1	30.4	88.3%	↓	+25°C	
SLIGHT CABLE WATER LEAK - PIPES EXITING CHILLER BOX.								
140715	R6	500'	10.0	29.3	71.7%	↓	+15°C	
140845	R6	500'	10.1	32.4	89%	↑	+17°C	Chiller to +25°C
141030	R6	500'	10.5	33.2	73.2%	↑	+30°C	
141310	R6	500'	10.4	30.8	78.4%	↑	+35°C	
141540	R6	500'	10.4	31.5	84.3%	↑	+40°C	
1417	R6	500'	10.4	27.3	87.5%	↑	+45°C	
141811	R65	500'	10.3	27.6	93.2%	↓	+45°C	Chiller to +0°C
142820	R65	500'	10.5	28.4	71.1%	↑	+16°C	142030 Brief labview glen ("San faded")
143021	R65	500'	10.5	27.8	76.1	↑	+30°C	Chiller to +25°C
143220	R65	500'	10.4	27.9	80.6	↑	+35°C	

Flight B245 15:22:30

Heading 306 deg Speed 4 knots Height 0.6kft Press 988mb
 Lat 52°0.0'N Long 0°30.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 312 deg
 Temp 27.17C Dewpoint 9.01C
 From 09:56 to 10:01:20

Current values				
—	INS HEADING	306.11	degT	☉ All
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	65.84	W m-2	☉
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	25.14	W m-2	☉

Upper BBR pre flight 360° rotation on Cranfield runway

Flight B245 15:22:30

Heading 306 deg Speed 4 knots Height 0.6kft Press 988mb
 Lat 52°0.0'N Long 0°30.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 312 deg
 Temp 27.17C Dewpoint 9.01C
 From 15:08:20 to 15:12

Current values				
—	INS HEADING	306.11	degT	☉ All
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	65.84	W m-2	☉
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	25.14	W m-2	☉
—	SOLAR AZIMUTH ANGLE	237.79	deg	☉

Upper BBR post flight 360° rotation on Cranfield runway

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B245**

Date: 21st September 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		Y
Heimann		Y	HVPS		
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC		
“ Red		Y	CVI		
“ Silicon		Y			
“ JO1D	n		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP		Y
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer		Y
“ Silicon		Y	Filters		N
“ JO1D			AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	n				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS		N
SWS	N		2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC	N		NOxy		N
PAN	N		PTRMS		N
PERCA	N		Bag Sampling		N
WAS	N		Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B245

Date: 21 September 2006

Instruments

FM's pc locked up – reset ok

Dry Neph data stuck at FFFFh on drs display. AERACK dlu found to be 'not sending packets'. DLU power cycled at aft core console & reset ok

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B245:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	Awaiting log
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of processing
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
Pre-Flighter log	No log available

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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